

1 **Histone expression changes during TE commitment, including macroH2A.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of key
9 changes in macroH2A during lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Buschbeck, M., Uribesalgo, I., Wibowo, I., Rué, P., Martin, D., Gutierrez, A., Morey, L., Guigó, R.,
12 López-Schier, H. and Di Croce, L., 2009. The histone variant macroH2A is an epigenetic regulator of key
13 developmental genes. *Nature structural & molecular biology*, 16(10), pp.1074-1079.